

BREAKING FRONTIERS IN SUSTAINABLE AND CIRCULAR BIOCOMPOSITES WITH HIGH PERFORMANCE.

For more info Scan here!

ABOUT US:

- 25** PARTNERS
- 12** COUNTRIES
- 36** MONTHS
- +8** MILLIONS EUROS OF BUDGET
- 6** SPECIFIC USE CASES

5 MAJOR OBJECTIVES:

SUSTAINABLE AND CIRCULAR DESIGN

INNOVATIVE AND SUSTAINABLE MATERIALS

MANUFACTURING TECHNOLOGIES AND PROTOTYPING

SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT AND END-OF-LIFE MANAGEMENT

AWARENESS AND MARKET ADOPTION

BIOntier CONSORTIUM:

MORE INFORMATION:

- www.biontier.eu
- BIONtier
- BIONtier

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